

Urethral Stricture model to estimate overdistention of healthy tissue.

Ashish Bhave^{1*}, Knut Möller¹

¹ Institute of Technical Medicine, Hochschule Furtwangen University, VS Schwenningen, Germany

* Ashish Bhave, email: ashishbhav1993@gmail.com

Abstract: To analyze the urethral wall properties, a new sensor-actuator system is being developed. The capabilities of this sensor shall be evaluated in simulations which requires appropriate modelling of the human male urethra for various conditions. As an initial approach, the urethra wall was modelled with fibre description following its multifold lumen. The pressure-stretch response was analyzed for a model of healthy urethra and an urethra with fibrosis. It was found that for sufficient extension, a larger dilation pressure is required which may cause overextension of the healthy part of the fibrotic urethra, leading to damage. This indicates simulation is a prospective way to test new devices prior to real experiments.

© Copyright 2021

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License CC-BY 4.0., which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

I. Introduction

Urethra is the tubular structure in the human genito-urinary tract which primarily allows passage of urine. Urethral stricture is hardening/constriction within the Urethra and is attributed to about 1.5 million doctor visits per year in the USA. Strictures result from injury to the epithelium of the urethra and/or underlying corpus spongiosum, which causes fibrosis during the healing process [1].

Strictures can be formed by catheterization, instrumentation, and prior hypospadias repair, infection, external injury, etc. Several methods for urethral dilation - to open the stricture, exist, that include dilation with a balloon, or dilation with catheters. Small tears in the metaplastic tissue of urethra during catheterization or balloon dilation may cause a fibrotic reaction within the spongiosum. When injured, fibrosis may show no symptoms; however, over time, the progressive fibrosis may cause narrowing of the lumen of the urethra, resulting in symptomatic obstructive voiding [1].

Few studies have evaluated the biomechanical behaviour of urethral tissue in planar tests and modelled its behaviour [2,3]. However there has been no attempts to model the behaviour of Male human urethra with its multifold shape and consideration of strictures. Currently a sensor-actuator setup is being developed at HFU, Germany that could provide circumferential expansion data of vessels. Forward modelling of urethra is an essential step to generate a large dataset for different situations. Construction of an urethral model based on the multifold in-vivo geometry of the urethra with stricture is the focus of this paper and could indicate that simulations provide a prospective way to test new devices prior to real experiments.

II. Material and methods

For the FEM simulations and analysis, COMSOL(v5.5) was chosen. As a first step, different constitutive models were evaluated for applicability to urethra or other similar vessels from literature studies. For its simplicity and robust applicability, the Holzapfel Gasser Ogden (HGO) model

was used to describe the anisotropic behaviour for fibre orientations within urethral walls (ref eq.1) [4]. The strain energy equation described for the isotropic part (W_{iso}) was chosen from Natali et al 2016, instead of the classical neo-hookean equation (ref eq.2.) [5]. $W(A)$ is the strain energy function based on the square of stretch of fibres. $A=1,2$ indicate the two different fibre orientations present in the urethral walls. k_1, k_2 are stress like parameters while α and k_2 are dimensionless constants. $Ist(A)$ is the stretch of the fibre.

$$W(A) = \frac{k_1}{2k_2} (e^{k_2(Ist(A)-1)^2} - 1) \quad (1)$$

$$W_{iso} = \frac{k}{\alpha} (e^{\alpha \epsilon} - 1) \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: The 3D model designed in COMSOL(L) and an example of cross section of the Urethra showing the Multifold structure.

The parameters values selected for the simulation were as follows: $k=5$ [kPa] $k_1= 2.5$ [kPa] $k_2=1$ $\alpha =1$ which have generated hyperelastic response. These values chosen are based on a range of biomechanical values for biological vessels like urethra and arteries but are not evaluated for their specificity.

The urethral wall has thickness of about $250\mu\text{m}$ -(from inner lumen wall to the adventitia) but is encircled by the corpus spongiosum that has thickness greater than 2mm and was to be included in the model [2]. Thus a 2.5mm sided square was created and extruded following the path of the folded lumen. 2 fibre orientations following the path of the hypothesized folded lumen structure ($\pm 5^\circ$ tilted) based on histological description were implemented [2]. The urethra

model was divided into four equal quadrants. For the first model simulation the urethra was assumed to be without fibrosis (increased hardness within the walls). Fibrosis is found to cause stress parameter to increase up to 10 times the normal values [6]. For the second model simulation the urethra was realized with fibrosis present in 2 adjacent quadrants which have parameter 'k' set to 50[kPa] for the hardness, other parameters being the same.

The upper and lower wall of the model is applied zero displacement condition in x and z axis. Zero displacement conditions were applied on four diametrically opposite edges along single directions, on the outer boundary of the model, to provide minimal constraints. Pressure was applied to the inner wall of the urethra and the pressure-stretch response were evaluated to observe differences for both the simulations.

III. Results and discussion

In Fig. 2, the response of the unaffected urethra is performed to evaluate its pressure-stretch response. Fig 3 shows the pressure-stretch response for the fibrotic region, the unaffected urethral region and the overall inner perimeter. The unaffected urethra shows a hyperelastic response to the applied pressure. At pressure of 50kPa, the stretch of the material exceeds 2.

Figure 2: The pressure-stretch response of the healthy unaffected urethra-model 1 simulation.

Figure 3: The pressure-stretch response of the hardened segment, healthy segment and overall response- model 2.

In the fig. 3 the urethra with 50% fibrosed (hardened) area, one can observe that the stretch for the 2 sections is intuitively, different. At 50 kPa, the total stretch of the urethral lumen is 1.6 while the stretch of the hardened segment is around only 1.4. The normal urethral segment

on the other hand has a stretch of 1.9. As the fibrosis tissue has more collagen tissue, even a stretch of 1.4 may cause further hardening to the tissue [3,6].

As mentioned by Cunnane et al., a stretch of over 1.7 caused the urethra to rupture or cause tears within the walls of healthy urethra [3]. From the results, it is observed that the unaffected urethra is more compliant than the one with fibrosis. The results for the fibrotic urethra indicate that a larger inner pressure is required to achieve a similar total extension as for the healthy one, resulting in overstretch of the healthy tissue. This may lead to fibrosis and severe strictures in the long run. Balloon dilators with comparatively higher pressures or self-dilating catheters with certain diameters may lead to injury to a fibrosed urethra, which is inferred from the overall stretch-healthy tissue stretch ratio.

IV. Conclusions

For the pressure range applied, in the simulation of the normal urethra, a stretch of 2 was found while in the simulation of urethra with fibrosis, the healthy tissue stretched up to 1.9 times while the fibrosis segment and the overall stretch was 1.4 and 1.6 respectively. In the fibrotic urethral model, it is deduced, that if one wants to have a larger overall stretch, a larger force is required, and it would cause overdistention to the healthy tissue. The equations and the parameters chosen, have a large impact on the behaviour of the vessel biomechanics. The models and their parameters chosen are demonstrative in nature and show an approach to in-vivo vessel modelling. Other tissues surrounding the urethra and its properties would impact the stretch response. Boundary conditions could be modified giving different outputs and a different analysis.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was partially supported by the German Federal Ministry of Research and Education (BMBF) under grant no. 13FH51051A (CoHMed/Digitalization in the OR).

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hampson, L.A., McAninch, J.W. and Breyer, B.N. *Male urethral strictures and their management*. Nature Reviews Urology, 11(1), 2014, pp.43-50.
- [2] Masri, C., Chagnon, G., Favier, D., Sartelet, H. and Girard, E. *Experimental characterization and constitutive modeling of the biomechanical behaviour of male human urethral tissues validated by histological observations*. Biomechanics and modeling in mechanobiology, 17(4), 2018, pp.939-950.
- [3] Cunnane, E.M., Davis, N.F., Cunnane, C.V., Lorentz, K.L., Ryan, A.J., Hess, J., Weinbaum, J.S., Walsh, M.T., O'Brien, F.J. and Vorp, D.A. *Mechanical, compositional and morphological characterisation of the human male urethra for the development of a biomimetic tissue engineered urethral scaffold*. Biomaterials, 269, 2021, p.120651.
- [4] Holzapfel, G.A., Gasser, T.C. and Ogden, R.W.. A new constitutive framework for arterial wall mechanics and a comparative study of material models. *Journal of elasticity and the physical science of solids*, 61(1), 2000, pp.1-48.
- [5] Natali, A.N., Carniel, E.L., Frigo, A., Pavan, P.G., Todros, S., Pachera, P., Fontanella, C.G., Rubini, A., Cavicchioli, L., Avital, Y. and De Benedictis, G.M.. *Experimental investigation of the biomechanics of urethral tissues and structures*. Experimental physiology, 101(5), 2016, pp.641-656.
- [6] Wells, R.G. *Tissue mechanics and fibrosis*. Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Molecular Basis of Disease, 1832(7), 2013, pp.884-890.